

INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR:

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Edited by:

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24-25 May 2023

Bragança, Portugal

Published in Bragança, Portugal
May, 2023

Title

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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Printed by

BRINGRÁFICA Indústrias Gráficas, LDA
Rua Arquiteto Viana de Lima, nº 53
5300-678 Bragança

Publisher

Instituto Politécnico de Bragança
Campus de Santa Apolónia
5300-253 Bragança
Portugal

Edition year: 2023

ISBN: 978-972-745-320-7 (Electronic version)

Handle: <http://hdl.handle.net/10198/1787>

URL: <https://esa.ipb.pt/artisanefood-seminar>

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Dynamic Modelling for Ensuring Microbiological Safety of Artisanal Fermented Foods

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Abstract

The fermentation and maturation processes of artisanal foods can be effectively controlled and regulated to provide microbiological stability to the products without the need for heat treatment, but instead based solely on the physicochemical changes during ripening that act as hurdles to undesirable microflora. The objective of this presentation is to show how dynamic predictive microbiology can be applied to characterise the kinetics of foodborne pathogens in artisanal fermented foods. Data obtained from fate studies of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Portuguese raw sausages formulated with 0.0%, 0.5%, 1.0% and 1.5% annatto (*Bixinia orellana* L.) extracts are taken as example.

The dynamic model proposed consists of a log-decay with tail model in differential form as primary model, and a Bigelow model of the D values as a function of pH as secondary model.

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = -kN \left(\frac{1}{1 + C_c} \right) \left(1 - \frac{N_{res}}{N} \right)$$

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = -kC_c$$

$$D = \frac{\ln(10)}{k}$$

$$\log D = \log D_{ref} - \left(\frac{pH - pH_{ref}}{z_{pH}} \right)$$

Such a dynamic model adequately described all survival curves. The addition of annatto extract produced log D* (at reference pH=7.0) slightly higher (1.040 [SE=0.064], 1.040 [SE=0.294] and 1.079 [SE=0.303]) than the control (1.036 [SE=0.142]), whereas z_{pH} tended to be lower with increasing extracts doses (2.426 [SE=0.561], 2.144 [SE=0.230], 2.113 [SE=1.033] and 2.005 (SE=0.904)). Therefore, the addition of annatto extract significantly decreased the time to achieve one log reduction, which in practical terms corresponded to up to 1.04 [SE=0.08] log CFU/g reduction by the end of maturation.

Keywords: Log-decay model with tail; Bigelow model; D-value; z_{pH}

Supporting Funds: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisanefood (PRIMA/0001/2018): Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods, funded by the EU PRIMA program and the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal). The authors are grateful to FCT for financial support through national funds FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2021).